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Key Points:

- An Eigen-Decomposition model of the thermospheric mass density is constructed based on the Swarm-C satellite observations
- The model characterizes density variability as a function of longitude, latitude, local time, season, and solar and geomagnetic activity
- Eigen-Decomposition model performs better than the JB2008 model and its capture efficiency is higher than that of the NRLMSIS2.0 model

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Eigen-Swarm: Swarm's Thermospheric Mass Density Modeling via Eigen-Decomposition

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Abstract Precise thermospheric mass density (TMD) prediction is essential for satellite orbital tracking, reentry calculations, and upper atmospheric processes under varying solar and magnetospheric conditions. In this paper, we construct an empirical model of TMD at 450 km altitude with accelerometer-derived (ACC) TMD observations from the Swarm-C satellite during 2014–2020. We employ the Eigen-Decomposition technique to extract dominant spatio-temporal modes, with the first three capturing 99.12% of the variance, forming the basis of the Swarm-based Eigen-Decomposition model. We study the factors controlling the observed TMD variability and investigate their relation to longitude, latitude, local solar time, seasonal effects, solar and geomagnetic indices. The Eigen-Decomposition model performance is validated by comparison with the Jacchia-Bowman 2008 (JB2008), Naval Research Laboratory Mass Spectrometer Incoherent Scatter 2.0 (NRLMSIS2.0), and Calabia and Jin (CAJIN) models, as well as TMD data from the Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment Follow-On mission during 2018–2020, using root mean square error (RMSE) as the evaluation metric. The Eigen-Decomposition model achieves an RMSE of 19.45%, outperforming JB2008 (29.83%), NRLMSIS2.0 (65.16%), and CAJIN (45.25%). Additional metrics, including correlation coefficient (R), mean (μ), and variance (σ^2), further confirm the improved accuracy and fidelity of our approach across different solar activity conditions. This work demonstrates the effectiveness of data-driven techniques in capturing TMD dynamics and deepening our understanding of the thermospheric response to space weather conditions.

Plain Language Summary Accurate prediction of thermospheric mass density (TMD) is vital for safeguarding satellite operations from space weather impacts and also provides critical information about satellite drags. Recent events, such as the loss of 38 satellites by SpaceX due to a geomagnetic storm, have highlighted the importance of having more accurate estimation and prediction of TMD variability. While several empirical models are used to predict TMD changes, they often struggle to accurately capture the TMD variability, especially during the geomagnetic storms, highlighting the need for continuous validation and improvement. Using the Eigen-Decomposition and regression techniques, the dominant modes of TMD variability from Swarm-C observations (2014–2020) were extracted and parameterized with respect to external drivers to develop the Eigen-Decomposition model. The newly developed model effectively reproduces TMD variability when validated against traditional empirical models and independent TMD observations. Our findings advance our understanding of thermospheric dynamics and enhance predictions crucial for satellite operations and space weather monitoring.

1. Introduction

As the number of anthropogenic space objects in the low-Earth orbit (LEO) grows, accurate modeling of the global thermospheric variability for orbit prediction becomes more important, especially for space weather forecasting and monitoring. Understanding thermospheric mass density (TMD) variability is crucial for comprehending the Sun-Earth interaction and its detrimental impacts on LEO satellites. The primary source of uncertainty in predicting satellite orbits in the Earth's upper atmosphere is TMD variability, which is characterized by various disturbances that originate from multiple forcing mechanisms (e.g., Calabia et al., 2023; Krauss et al., 2015; Oliveira & Zesta, 2019; Yu et al., 2020). Such mechanisms include the diurnal and seasonal cycles from the variable solar irradiance, the electromagnetic energy deposited in the high-latitude atmosphere due to

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solar wind-magnetosphere coupling, and effects from the lower and middle atmosphere (e.g., Bowman et al., 2008; Burns et al., 2021; Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Oliveira et al., 2017). At high latitudes, the TMD variability is primarily influenced by Joule heating and energetic electron precipitation, while also being affected by other factors such as winds, plasma turbulence, and variable electric fields and conductivity (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2019; Oliveira & Zesta, 2024; Sutton et al., 2012; Weimer, 2005). On the other hand, in the lower latitude regions, the TMD variability is more actively driven by the solar extreme ultraviolet (EUV) irradiance and the soft X-ray flux (e.g., Sutton et al., 2006; Vourlidas & Bruinsma, 2018). These features make the characterization and modeling of TMD dynamics, a key parameter for orbit prediction, difficult, while our modern society strongly depends on space assets (e.g., Acciarini et al., 2024; Oliveira et al., 2021). A new motivator for accurate TMD forecasts is satellite collision avoidance. SpaceX alone performed >100,000 collision avoidance maneuvers in 2024, and all conjunction assessment and collision avoidance capability in LEO is severely degraded during geomagnetic storms because we couldn't accurately predict satellite trajectories due to variable drag (especially during the Gannon storm). The important role of TMD in precise orbit determination and atmospheric research has forced researchers from all over the world to study the spatio-temporal characteristics of TMD with empirical and physics-based modeling (e.g., Acciarini et al., 2024; Calabia et al., 2020; Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Gondelach & Linares, 2021; Lei et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2013; Matsuo & Forbes, 2010; Oliveira et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2020).

Accurate monitoring and prediction of TMD variability is a challenging task, involving many variables and a multitude of available techniques, and several atmospheric models are currently in use for the dynamics of the thermosphere-ionosphere system. Some well-known empirical models developed over the years are the Naval Research Laboratory Mass Spectrometer Incoherent Scatter 2.0 (NRLMSIS2.0) (e.g., Picone et al., 2002), Jacchia-Bowman 2008 (JB2008) (e.g., Bowman et al., 2007), High Accuracy Satellite Drag Model (HASDM) (e.g., Tobiska et al., 2021), and Drag-Temperature Model DTM-2013 (e.g., Bruinsma, 2015), which are currently in use for practical applications such as the implementation of drag in precise orbit determination. For several years, these models have been improved with respect to earlier versions (e.g., Emmert et al., 2020), since large uncertainties usually occur, especially during geomagnetic storms (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016a; Fang et al., 2022; He et al., 2023; Marcos, 1990; Oliveira et al., 2021). Due to the importance of TMD in spacecraft operation, especially for LEO satellites, researchers have explored its spatial and temporal properties of TMD and developed empirical models using methods such as machine learning (e.g., Acciarini et al., 2024; Weng et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021), dynamic reduced-order modeling (e.g., Mehta et al., 2018), data assimilation (e.g., Matsuo et al., 2012) and the Thermosphere-Ionosphere Electrodynamics General Circulation Model, yielding significant results (e.g., Elvidge et al., 2016). Over the past years, substantial research has improved TMD variability estimation during either quiet or stormy time conditions (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Lei et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2013), since even moderate geomagnetic storms can significantly impact satellite orbital drag (e.g., Baruah et al., 2024; Lin et al., 2022). The ACC-derived TMDs from CHAMP (CHALLENGING Minisatellite Payload), Swarm and twin-GRACE (Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment) showed that the accuracy of existing empirical models is limited, especially during space weather events (e.g., Liu et al., 2005; Oliveira et al., 2021; Sutton et al., 2007).

In an effort to account for new TMD data in the models, different modeling approaches have been used, including, for example, the use of the Eigen-Decomposition analysis, usually known as Principal Component Analysis in geophysics, or Empirical Orthogonal Function analysis in climate studies (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Gondelach & Linares, 2021; Lei et al., 2012; Matsuo & Forbes, 2010; Owolabi et al., 2021, 2022). Here we will name the method by its original form, namely the Eigen-Decomposition method. For instance, Lei et al. (2012) investigated annual and semiannual variations using a sequential nonlinear regression analysis of TMD data from CHAMP and GRACE at 400 km altitude during 2002–2010. The authors highlighted the capabilities of their method in capturing significant temporal patterns and spatial structures in TMD data, offering a refined understanding of its behavior under different conditions. The authors discovered a correlation between TMD and NRLMSIS-00 changes with geographic location, season, and solar-geomagnetic activity. In Sutton et al. (2012), the authors developed a series of dominant functions to better capture the spatial variability and response of the thermosphere to improve the HASDM model accuracy in TMD prediction. They improved HASDM calibration with sparse data, reducing the root mean square error (RMSE) by 32.9% relative to synthetic data. A study by Liu et al. (2013) employed in situ measurements of TMD from CHAMP satellite and constructed a model that empirically investigates the solar impact of TMD. Their findings indicate a significant correlation between the equinoctial asymmetry of TMD and the solar cycle, wherein the magnitude and phase of the asymmetry are heavily influenced by different levels of solar and geomagnetic activity.

Using a grid-based technique, Calabia and Jin (2016b) applied Eigen-Decomposition to dimensionally reduce 13 years of ACC-derived TMD from the GRACE mission. They analyzed the resulting principal modes and parameterized them according to solar and magnetospheric forcing, local solar time (LST), and annual variations to create an empirical model available in MATLAB language. This model was later upgraded with a parameterized magnetospheric forcing in Calabia and Jin (2019), hereafter named the CAJIN model. Their parameterizations were suitable to represent small-scale variations, including, for example, the equatorial mass density anomaly (EMA) and the midnight density maximum, and the residuals showed additional contributions at the frequencies of the radiational tides and at the periods of 83, 93, 152, and 431 days. Then, in Calabia et al. (2020), the authors used Swarm-C data to make several orbit predictions and analyses. They found that the NRLMSISE-00 model overestimates the in situ TMD by about 20%, while the CAJIN model underestimates it by the same amount. Yang et al. (2022) developed an empirical model to predict TMD variability from 2002 to 2010 using CHAMP and GRACE observations, which showed better agreement with independent GRACE-A observations than NRLMSIS-00, accurately capturing EMA and seasonal variations. Similarly, Xiong et al. (2018) introduced CH-Therm-2018, based on nine years of CHAMP data (2000–2009), which outperformed NRLMSIS-00 in capturing TMD variability, particularly during the 2008–2009 solar minimum.

Despite considerable advances in TMD model formulation over the years, there is a gap for model improvement in terms of performance and accuracy. This improvement is necessary to surpass the level of agreement achieved by existing models in practical applications (e.g., Calabia et al., 2020; Marcos, 1990). The TMD discrepancy between models and data suggests the need for a better understanding of the Sun–Earth system. Thus, researchers need to keep track of geomagnetic and solar components that affect TMD variability to improve present models and benchmarks. The previous solar cycle (2009–2020) is uniquely quiet compared to other solar cycles and thus the Eigen-Decomposition model may give insight into thermosphere responses during our recent quiet solar cycle. Here, in this paper, we present a new TMD model based on the Eigen-Decomposition of ACC-derived data from 2014 to 2020. The Eigen-Decomposition model differs from previous work by (a) focusing on a quiet solar cycle, which provides an opportunity to isolate and characterize thermospheric variability under weak solar and geomagnetic forcing conditions; (b) parameterizing TMD by latitude, longitude, LST, and day of year (DOY) to resolve fine-scale structures; and (c) benchmarking against JB2008, NRLMSIS2.0, and CAJIN under various solar and geomagnetic conditions. Unlike the JB2008 and NRLMSIS2.0 models built on fixed empirical relationships derived from historical data, our adaptive statistical approach can evolve with new data and uncover latent structures. In principle, this comparative approach highlights the strengths and limitations of existing models under quiet conditions. The next section details the data and methods used in this study, followed by the Eigen-Decomposition model results and discussion in Section 4. The paper concludes with a summary in the final section.

2. Data and Method

2.1. Data and Empirical Atmospheric Models

In this study, we utilized the ACC-derived TMD from the Swarm-C satellite to construct an Eigen-Decomposition model. The ACC-derived TMD offers higher temporal resolution and captures finer-scale variability. The Swarm mission comprises constellation of three identical satellites named Alpha (A), Bravo (B), and Charlie (C), launched into near-polar LEO on 22 November 2013 (e.g., Siemes et al., 2016). These satellites primarily study geomagnetic fields and are equipped with accelerometers positioned at their centers of mass to collect TMD data crucial for understanding Earth's thermosphere dynamics (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Kodikara et al., 2018). Swarm-A and -C orbit at an altitude of ~ 462 km in near-polar orbits (inclination 87.35°). The two satellites are separated by approximately 1.4° in longitude at the equator due to their slightly offset orbital planes. Swarm-B orbits at a higher altitude of ~ 510 – 530 km with an inclination of 87.75° , resulting in a longer orbital period of ~ 94.5 min compared to ~ 93 min for Swarm-A and -C satellites. Different local time precession rates apply to Swarm-A, -B, and -C satellites as follows: The 2 lower satellites precess through 12 hr of local time in 133 days, while the upper spacecraft precesses through 12 hr in 144 days, resulting in a local time separation of 10 hr after 5 years of mission duration. In October 2021, the orbital planes realigned, with Swarm B orbiting in the opposite direction of Swarms A and C satellites. We also used TMD data from the Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment Follow-On (GRACE-FO) mission, a joint NASA and the German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ) initiative launched on 22 May 2018, as GRACE's successor. It consists of two identical satellites flying ~ 220 km apart in a polar orbit at ~ 500 km altitude (e.g., Bandikovaa et al., 2019; Ciraci et al., 2020; Landerer

et al., 2020). Global TMD data, available at higher spatial and temporal resolutions, are freely accessible and widely used for TMD estimation (<https://swarm-diss.eo.esa.int>).

To validate the Eigen-Decomposition model outputs, we estimated TMD values from JB2008, NRLMSIS2.0 and CAJIN models along the Swarm-C satellite's orbit (2014–2020). The NRLMSIS2.0 and JB2008 models are empirical and semi-empirical frameworks that rely on long-term historical data sets and established physical relationships. NRLMSIS2.0 for instance, is an updated thermospheric model (0–1,000 km) based on satellite and ground-based radar observations. It characterizes the upper atmosphere, providing altitude-dependent exospheric and neutral temperatures and TMD. It takes inputs such as altitude, latitude, longitude, DOY, LST, daily and 81-day averaged F10.7 flux, and Ap index. On the other hand, the JB2008 is tailored for satellite drag prediction and incorporates solar and geomagnetic indices to model TMD. It includes empirical corrections for storm-time effects and diurnal variations, making it robust for operational use in space weather forecasting. Compared to NRLMSIS2.0, it incorporates additional solar proxies S10.7 (26–34 nm bandpass EUV chromospheric irradiance index), M10.7 (160 nm FUV Schumann-Runge photospheric irradiance proxy), Y10.7 (121.6 nm Lyman-alpha chromospheric region irradiance convolved with the 0.1–0.8 nm X-ray coronal irradiance), their 81-day averages, and geomagnetic indices (Ap, Dst) (e.g., Tobiska et al., 2008). Using the NRLMSIS2.0 model, Swarm-C observations were normalized to a height of 450 km in order to exclude TMD variability caused by changes in satellite orbital altitude, as follows: $\rho(450\text{km}) = \rho(z) * \frac{\rho_m(450\text{km})}{\rho_m(z)}$. In this equation, ρ_m is the NRLMSIS2.0 estimate, and z is Swarm-C satellite height. The normalization error should be low. Liu et al. (2007) found 5% uncertainty acceptable in multi-year comparisons, especially when the spacecraft's altitude shift is negligible (e.g., Bruinsma et al., 2023).

2.2. Space Weather Indices and Formulation of the TMD Model

To develop a reliable empirical model of TMD, it is essential to incorporate key space weather drivers that influence upper atmospheric variability. In this study, we utilize the Mg II core-to-wing index from the Solar Radiation and Climate Experiment (SORCE) as a sensitive proxy for solar activity, along with the planetary geomagnetic Ap index to account for geomagnetic disturbances. The MgII core-to-wing index, scaled as $M10.7 = 8,083 \times \text{MgII}-1,154$ provides a more reliable proxy for solar activity than the F10.7 flux (e.g., Ruan et al., 2018; Viereck et al., 2001) and has been shown to effectively represent solar activity influences on TMD variability (e.g., Solomon et al., 2011). The Eigen-Decomposition model is constructed using M10.7p, M10.7A, Ap and ApD indices. Where M10.7p refers to the daily M10.7 index for the day before, M10.7A represents the 81-day average value centered on the current day, and ApD stands for the daily averaged 3-hr Ap index. Figure 1c shows the daily and 81-day averaged solar M10.7 index, which ranges from 243 to 60 sfu for different solar activity levels. The 3-hr Ap index obtained from the OMNI webpage, shown in Figure 1d, also varies during this investigation and is higher during high solar activity. We apply the Eigen-Decomposition approach to decompose the time-varying $\text{TMD}(\text{lon}, \text{lat}, t)$ into a set of mutually orthogonal spatial base functions $\phi_n(\text{lon}, \text{lat})$ and time series $\alpha_n(t)$ as described in numerous studies (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Lei et al., 2012; Ruan et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2020). In this study, we extracted the first three dominant spatio-temporal modes, which collectively explained 99.12% of the total variance. Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$\text{TMD}(\text{lon}, \text{lat}, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{n=M} \alpha_n(t) * \phi_n(\text{lon}, \text{lat}) \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, M) \quad (1)$$

where $\text{TMD}(\text{lon}, \text{lat}, t)$ is the observed TMD for certain longitude, latitude, and time, $\alpha_n(t)$ is the component's amplitude that varies with respect to time, t , and $\phi_n(\text{lon}, \text{lat})$ is the nth Eigen mode that varies as a function of geographic longitude and latitude. Our approach involves grid-based Eigen-Decomposition followed by the computation of the covariance matrix across the grid, akin to the method used by Calabia and Jin (2016b) and Ruan et al. (2018). The spatial vector $\text{TMD}(\text{lon}, \text{lat})$ is represented by $M \times N$ elements on a regular grid of $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$, and $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is the modal index, which is less than or equal to M . Our method involves using a two-dimensional matrix where each row represents LST and each column represents a time series for a specific latitude. Each daily global grid, spanning from 2014 to 2020, has been transformed into a one-dimensional array ($72 \times 36 = 2,592$). These arrays were concatenated from ascending and descending satellite orbits to form a consolidated data set, resulting in a final matrix size of $2,592 \times 9,524$. By analyzing the covariance structure of

Figure 1. (a–c) Leading orthogonal components of the thermospheric mass density (PC1–PC3) at 450 km altitude derived from Swarm-C observations (2014–2020) in unit of 10^{-2} as a function of longitude and latitudes and (d) their relative contributions to the total variance.

TMD, our method identifies dominant modes of variability, essentially capturing how different regions or parameters co-vary over time. This technique allows for dimensionality reduction and pattern recognition without relying on predefined physical laws. It is particularly powerful for uncovering regional or temporal anomalies and can adapt flexibly to new data sets, making it well-suited for localized or evolving atmospheric phenomena. We parameterize $\alpha_n(t)$ for each mode spanning from 2014 to 2020, incorporating periodic oscillations such as annual, semi-annual, and terannual variations using harmonic functions. The LST variation includes 24, 12, and 8h components. The change in the harmonic amplitudes is related to the solar flux and geomagnetic indices, as indicated in Equation 2, accounting for solar cycle dependence and geomagnetic activity. The unknown coefficients $a, b, c, d, p,$ and q are derived through linear regression by minimizing the sum of squared differences between the observed values of α and the values predicted by the regression equation. The calculated coefficients are then integrated into the regression equation, together with the input variables (LON, LAT, DOY, LST, M10.7A, M10.7p, Ap, ApD, and first three modes) to reconstruct and provide accurate predictions of TMD values.

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \alpha_n &= X_s * Y_s \\
 X_s &= (a_o + a_1 * M10.7p + a_2 * M10.7A + a_3 * M10.7p * M10.7A) (b_o + b_1 * Ap + b_2 * ApD) \\
 Y_s &= c_0 + \sum_{k=1}^3 \left(p_k \cos \left(\frac{2\pi * DOY * k}{365.25} \right) + q_k \sin \left(\frac{2\pi * DOY * k}{365.25} \right) \right) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{k=1}^3 \left(c_k \cos \left(\frac{2\pi * LST * k}{24} \right) + d_k \sin \left(\frac{2\pi * LST * k}{24} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where X_s depends on solar and geomagnetic activity effects, Y_s is referred to as UT/longitude and the seasonality parameter which signifies the inter-annual variations, c_0 is the mean value of α_n . Here p_k and q_k ($k = 1, 2, 3$) represent the annual, semiannual and terannual variations of the TMD variations, c_k and d_k ($k = 1, 2, 3$) indicate the diurnal, semidiurnal and terdiurnal variations, LST stands for current LST in hours, including the diurnal, semidiurnal, and terdiurnal variations; and DOY represents the number of days from January 2014 to December 2020, encompassing the annual, semiannual, and terannual variations. Leap years were accounted for by adding a 0.25-factor to the 365-day calculation. To assess performance, we compared TMD predictions from the Eigen-Decomposition model against JB2008, MSIS2.0, and CAJIN models using key metrics that quantify how well each model captures TMD variability. These include RMSE, correlation coefficient (R), mean (μ), and variance (σ^2). Here are the equations for these metrics:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{RMSE} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=1}^h (\text{TMD}_i^{\text{obs}} - \text{TMD}_i^{\text{mod}})^2} \\ R &= \frac{\text{Cov}(\text{TMD}_i^{\text{mod}}, \text{TMD}_i^{\text{obs}})}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(\text{TMD}_i^{\text{mod}}) * \text{Var}(\text{TMD}_i^{\text{obs}})}} \\ \mu &= \frac{1}{h} \sum_i^n \text{TMD}_i^{\text{obs}} \\ \sigma^2 &= \frac{1}{h} \sum_i^n (\text{TMD}_i^{\text{obs}} - \mu)^2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where h is the number of observations, $\text{TMD}_i^{\text{mod}}$ and $\text{TMD}_i^{\text{obs}}$ are the i th actual and predicted TMD values, μ is the mean of TMD values, Cov and Var denote covariance and variance, respectively. We used TMD data from the GRACE-FO mission spanning 1 May 2018 to 31 December 2020 for model validation.

3. Model Results and Discussion

Figures 1a–1c shows the global distribution of the first three dominant modes (ϕ) that determine spatial TMD variability in geographic coordinates, while Figure 1d shows the relative contribution of the top 5 spatial modes. The first orthogonal mode (ϕ_1) retains 96.82%, the second orthogonal mode (ϕ_2) retains 1.29%, and the third orthogonal mode (ϕ_3) retains 1.01% of the total variability. In total, the first 3 modes account for 99.12% of the total variance. It is evident that each mode represents the main spatial features of TMD variability. For example, the equatorial anomaly feature is pictured in the first mode (Figure 1a), with the TMD peak in the southern polar region and other peaks appearing in the equatorial region around 0° longitude. The maximum values are situated at the southern cusp, while the minimum values are found at the northern cusp. It can be inferred that the distribution is associated with the orientation of the dip angle, resulting in positive TMD contributions in the southern cusp and negative contributions in the northern cusp (e.g., Lei et al., 2012). Since the first component contributes 96.82% of overall variance, its global average mode is significant. The second and third modes show north/south dominance of TMD variability. They exhibit different patterns in the northern and southern hemispheres, suggesting that it could be a seasonal variation in the thermosphere.

As previously noted in Liu et al. (2009), the second and third modes clearly relate to changes in latitudinal variations caused by LST as well as latitudinal variations following the subsolar point. Figures 2a, 2c, and 2e display the temporal variations of the first 3 modes (α_{1-3}) for the ascending orbit, whereas Figures 2b, 2d, and 2f mirror the same variations for the descending orbit. It is evident that the (α_{1-3}) contains clear annual and semiannual variations that are much more obvious in the higher-order modes. Notably, their (α_{1-3}) amplitudes gradually increase from 2014 to 2020 and are solar cycle dependent, which correlates with the first three temporal coefficients parameterized in terms of longitude, latitude, LST, DOY, M10.7p, M10.7A, Ap, and ApD with correlation values of 99%, 96%, and 93%, respectively. As seen by the red solid lines and the correlation values, the regression analysis results are well parameterized and aid the TMD reconstruction. Figures 2g and 2h are an identical plot of the solar irradiance proxy M10.7 index and M10.7A. Figures 2i and 2j are also identical plots and

Figure 2. Temporal functions representing the PC 1–3 amplitudes derived from Swarm-C observations fitting (blue dots) and the parameterization results (red lines) for ascending (a, c, e) and descending (b, d, f) orbits during 2014–2020. (g and h) Time series of the daily M10.7 (or $M10.7_{\text{eff}} = (M10.7 + M10.7A)/2$) index in gray and its 81-running average (M10.7A) in red. (i and j) The daily average of geomagnetic activity index Ap (i.e., ApD) between 2014 and 2020.

show the daily average of the 3-hourly Ap index during this period. As illustrated in this Figure, the M10.7 flux ranged from 80 solar flux units (sfu) in 2014 to about 140 sfu in 2015. The Ap index varied significantly during 2014–2020, and its variability is more profound during the period of high solar activity in 2014–2016 and becomes lower at low solar activity in 2018–2020. Figure 3 shows the TMD obtained from Swarm-C satellite (magenta dot), alongside statistical results from the JB2008 model (blue line), NRLMSIS2.0 model (gray line), and CAJIN model (black line). As shown in Figure 3a, the Eigen-Decomposition model (red dot) captures overall TMD variability seen in the Swarm-C observations by using the following input parameters: M10.7p, M10.7A, Ap, ApD, longitude, latitude, LST, and DOY. Furthermore, the TMDs estimated from the Eigen-Decomposition model exhibit a temporal variation i.e. closer to the Swarm-C values than those estimated by the MSIS2.0 and CAJIN models. As shown in Figure 3a, the absolute TMD estimates increase with solar activity because the thermosphere is heated by solar radiation as well as geomagnetic activity and expands to higher altitudes.

Note that the Swarm-C observations were not used when the JB2008 and MSIS2.0 models were developed (e.g., Bowman et al., 2007; Emmert et al., 2020). Figure 3b shows the model-to-data ratio of TMD obtained by the Eigen-Decomposition model (red line), JB2008 (blue line), MSIS2.0 (gray line) and CAJIN (black line). This ratio is calculated along with standard deviation between the TMD from the models and Swarm-C observations $[(\text{TMD data} - \text{Model value}) / \text{Model value}]$. The Eigen-Decomposition model shows a good model-to-TMD data ratio of 0.8–1.1, while the JB2008 and CAJIN models show the ratio of 1.2–1.5, and MSIS2.0 shows the ratio of 1.3–2.5, respectively. Comparatively, the seasonal-averaged ratios between the Eigen-Decomposition model and

Figure 3. (a) Orbit-averaged thermospheric mass density (TMD) derived from Swarm-C observations (black) normalized to 450 km from 2014 to 2020, compared with the Eigen-Decomposition model (red), Jacchia-Bowman 2008 (JB2008) (blue), NRLMSIS2.0 (gray), and CAJIN (black) models. (b) Seasonal mean ratios and standard deviations between model estimates and Swarm-C observations. (c) Statistical distribution of relative TMD errors for the four models. (d–e) Latitudinal and longitudinal variability of TMD, with error bars, comparing Eigen-Decomposition, NRLMSIS2.0, JB2008, and CAJIN models. Root mean square error = root-mean-square error.

Swarm-C observations are within $\pm 20\%$, while MSIS2.0 overestimates from 5% for high (2014:2015) and moderate (2015:2016) solar activity to 40% during low solar (2017:2020) activity periods. Another thing worth noting is that the Eigen-Decomposition model, JB2008 and MSIS2.0 models have a higher precision and applicability in the years 2014–2015 (high solar activity period) than in the year 2020 (low solar activity period), which are consistent with previous studies (e.g., Ruan et al., 2018). We observed that models approaching a quotient near one exhibit lower errors compared to observations. The MSIS2.0 shows poor performance for low-density values during 2018–2021, while JB2008 and CAJIN remain within a 0.5 deviation. Notably, CAJIN shows better agreement with Swarm-C observations under certain conditions, especially during periods of moderate geomagnetic activity. This advantage can be attributed to CAJIN being a recent data-driven model trained on a more extensive data set, including post-2014 satellite observations such as Swarm and CHAMP observations. Figure 3c shows the statistical distribution of model-Swarm-C daily mean TMD relative errors. The RMSE of the TMD from the Eigen-Decomposition model, JB2008, MSIS2.0, and CAJIN models are recorded to be 19.45%, 29.83%, 65.16%, and 45.25%, respectively. The RMSE value of the Eigen-Decomposition model is the smallest, when compared to JB2008, MSIS2.0, and CAJIN (Figure 3c), implying that the Eigen-Decomposition model predicts TMD better. Figures 3d and 3e show latitudinal and longitudinal behavior of the TMD deviation with error bars from Swarm-C data for the Eigen-Decomposition model (red), MSIS2.0 (gray), JB2008 (blue line) and CAJIN (black line) models. In Figures 3d and 3e, the MSIS2.0 model exhibits a 60% deviation at equatorial and low latitudes and 52% at middle and high latitudes. As for the performance of MSIS2.0, its deviation may stem from limitations in its composition and temperature parameterizations, particularly during disturbed conditions. Specifically, the fixed relationships used for neutral species (e.g., O, N₂) and the response of exospheric temperature to geomagnetic activity may not fully capture the dynamic variability of the thermosphere during solar maxima or storm-time periods (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Ruan et al., 2018). The Eigen-Decomposition model and CAJIN model have near-zero relative deviation in the latitudinal variation, better as compared to MSIS2.0 and JB2008 models. For longitudinal variation, the TMD relative deviation was about 55% and almost steady along longitudes. The MSIS2.0 model exhibits a relative deviation in TMD that is approximately twice as large as that observed in the JB2008 model and CAJIN has an interesting longitudinal variation centered at zero, suggesting that MSIS2.0 cannot accurately reproduce the longitudinal and latitudinal structures of TMD variability. Overall, Figure 3 indicates that the Eigen-Decomposition model reproduces the retrieved TMD variability better than the JB2008, MSIS2.0 and CAJIN models, consistent with previous studies

Figure 4. Scatter plots of the daily thermospheric mass density variability between models and Swarm-C observations at 450 km altitude; (a) Eigen-Decomposition model, (b) Jacchia-Bowman 2008 (JB2008) (c) MSIS2.0 and (d) CAJIN models. Histograms of model-observation deviation determined for individual models (blue bars) and Gaussian-function regression that best fits the empirical distribution (red line) for (e) Eigen-Decomposition model, (f) JB2008, (g) MSIS2.0, and (h) CAJIN models. The correlation coefficient (R), root-mean-square error (root mean square error), mean (μ) and variance (σ^2) are also given in the panels.

that demonstrated the improved performance of Eigen-Decomposition models in capturing real TMD behavior (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Lei et al., 2012). It is important to note that Figure 3 serves as a benchmark within the model's training domain. To assess generalizability, we highlight the independent evaluation presented in the next section, which utilizes data from a non-Swarm satellite.

Moreover, in order to further assess the performance of the Eigen-Decomposition model, Figures 4a–4d shows a scatter plot of daily TMD between models and Swarm-C observations, while Figures (4e–4h) shows a histogram of TMD deviation between models and Swarm-C observations. Each histogram of the relative deviation [(TMD data–Model value)/Model value] was fitted with a normal distribution to estimate the average TMD deviation and the variability across the data set. The upper right corners of Figures (4e–4h) show the mean deviation (μ) and variance (σ^2). The TMD shows a generally linear distribution with a positive slope (Figures 4a–4d) and the residuals follow a normal distribution (Figures 4e–4h). Furthermore, the majority of deviations (errors) for all the models are concentrated within the range of ± 2 kg/m³. In this Figure, the Eigen-Decomposition model has the lowest RMSE (0.084 kg/m³), suggesting the lowest average prediction error. It also has the highest correlation coefficient (0.990), showing it better captures data patterns and variability. The JB2008 model has a slightly higher RMSE (0.106 kg/m³) compared to the Eigen-Decomposition model, indicating marginally greater prediction error. While its correlation coefficient (0.988) remains high, it is slightly lower than that of the Eigen-Decomposition model, suggesting a modestly reduced ability to capture data variability. The MSIS2.0 model has a strong correlation with the Swarm-C observations (correlation coefficients can reach 0.962), which indicates that MSIS2.0 model is capable of representing the overall distributions and variability in the original TMD observations. In addition, the RMSE (0.181 kg/m³) shows some accuracy of the MSIS2.0 model. Among the four models, CAJIN has the highest RMSE (0.382 kg/m³), indicating the greatest average error. Its correlation coefficient (0.774) is lower than those of the Eigen-Decomposition model, JB2008, and MSIS2.0 models, indicating a modest ability to capture data variability. This is consistent with the findings of Calabia et al. (2020), which showed that CAJIN underestimates TMD values by approximately 20% compared to Swarm-C data. Conversely, the MSIS2.0 model tends to overestimate TMD. The JB2008 model shows slightly better correlation and accuracy than MSIS2.0, consistent with our findings. The Eigen-Decomposition model was further validated using

Figure 5. Scatterplots comparing the Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment Follow-On observations and modeled thermospheric mass density at 450 km altitude; (a) Eigen-Decomposition model, (b) Jacchia-Bowman 2008 (JB2008) and (c) MSIS2.0 models. Histograms for model-observation deviation (blue bars) and Gaussian-function regression that best fits the empirical distribution (red line) for (d) Eigen-Decomposition model, (e) JB2008 and (f) MSIS2.0 models. The correlation coefficient (R), root-mean-square error (root mean square error), mean (μ) and variance (σ^2) are also given in the panels.

independent GRACE-FO TMD observations (2018–2020) as shown in Figure 5, achieving the lowest RMSE (0.067 kg/m^3) compared to JB2008 (0.085 kg/m^3) and MSIS2.0 (0.139 kg/m^3). It also showed the highest correlation (0.681) with GRACE-FO, outperforming JB2008 (0.513) and MSIS2.0 (0.529). These results highlight the Eigen-Decomposition model's improved accuracy and its potential for real-time space weather and climate studies. We emphasize that this model is constructed solely from Swarm-C data, and not from GRACE-FO measurements.

To show the impact of solar activity on TMD variability, we compare four models with Swarm-C data during daytime (07:00–18:00 LST) and nighttime (18:00–06:00 LST), as shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. The Eigen-Decomposition model is based on Solar Cycle 24, characterized by low solar activity (the maximum sunspot number is ~ 100 sfu), unlike JB2008, MSIS2.0, and CAJIN, developed using data from more active cycles (more than 100 sfu during the solar maximum). The weaker TMD in the Eigen-Decomposition model reflects a cooler thermosphere. We can observe that the daytime TMD (Figure 6a–6o) peaks during the December solstice, with stronger March equinox TMD under higher solar activity. Nighttime TMD (Figure 7a–7o) is lowest in June and December, with semiannual variation peaking near equinoxes. The JB2008 captures this pattern well under low solar activity (Figure 6d), aligning with earlier observations (e.g., Guo et al., 2008). The Eigen-Decomposition model's accuracy is supported by GRACE-FO validation ($\text{RMSE} = 0.067 \text{ kg/m}^3$) and aligns with CHAMP/GRACE-based models like those by Yang et al. (2024), Lei et al. (2012), and Xiong et al. (2018). Compared to MSIS2.0, which overestimates TMD in quiet times, the Eigen-Decomposition model shows lower deviation and error. Although the Eigen-Decomposition model slightly underestimates TMD at high solar activity ($M10.7 = 160$ sfu), its accuracy across varying solar inputs suggests robust performance. Such underestimation is a known limitation of empirical models, reflecting the broader difficulty of capturing rapidly evolving thermospheric dynamics. The underestimation likely stems from limitations inherent to Eigen-Decomposition methods, which prioritize variance-maximizing, orthogonal modes and may miss localized or transient features. As shown in Figures 6 and 7, the Eigen-Decomposition model closely follows Swarm-C observations during both solar minimum and rising phases. This strong performance reflects not only the effectiveness of mode extraction but

Figure 6. Latitudinal and seasonal variations of daytime (07:18 LT) thermospheric mass density (10^{-12} kg/m^3) at 450 km altitude as a function of latitude and day of year derived from Swarm-C observations (a–c), Eigen-Decomposition model (d–f), JB2008 model (g–i), MSIS2.0 model (j–l), and CAJIN model (m–o) are presented respectively for low, moderate, and high solar activity conditions.

also the use of Swarm-C observations in model training. As with many empirical models, such performance may limit generalization (e.g., Calabia & Jin, 2016b; Ruan et al., 2018), highlighting the importance of validating the model against independent GRACE-FO to assess its broader applicability. The primary difference between Eigen-Decomposition model using Swarm-C observations ($\sim 450 \text{ km}$) and CAJIN's model based on GRACE-FO ($\sim 500 \text{ km}$) lies in the nature of the satellite missions, the type of data collected, and the spatial-temporal resolution

Figure 7. Same as Figure 6, but for nighttime (18:06 LT) thermospheric mass density (10^{-12} kg/m^3).

of the observations, which in turn influence the insights each model can provide. The Eigen-Decomposition model, benefits from finer spatial and temporal resolution, especially at lower altitude than GRACE-FO in the low-latitude and mid-latitude thermosphere and can capture short-term and localized variations in TMD dynamics more effectively than GRACE-FO. In essence, the Eigen-Decomposition model complements and extends CAJIN's work by leveraging a different observational platform with higher resolution and a different mission focus. This enables a more granular understanding of thermospheric variability, especially in regions and timescales where GRACE-FO data may be limited or smoothed out. Future improvements may involve machine learning and extending to geomagnetic storm conditions. Overall, the Eigen-Decomposition model captures TMD variability, confirming the cooler, thinner thermosphere during the quiet Solar Cycle 24 and enhancing our understanding of thermospheric dynamics.

4. Summary

This study presents an empirical TMD model based on ACC-derived TMD observations from the Swarm-C satellite (2014–2020), normalized to 450 km altitude. Using the Eigen-Decomposition technique and nonlinear least-squares fitting, the model captures TMD variability across solar conditions (M10.7 from >200 to <70 sfu). It describes TMD as a function of longitude, latitude, LST, DOY, Ap, ApD, M10.7p, and M10.7A. Compared to JB2008, MSIS2.0, and CAJIN models, as well as independent GRACE-FO observations, the Eigen-Decomposition model exhibits superior performance: 5% relative error and 1.2% standard deviation (vs. 15%/1.6% for JB2008 and 28%/2.5% for MSIS2.0). MSIS2.0 shows >50% longitudinal variation, while CAJIN has near-zero-centered variation ($R = 0.774$, $RMSE = 0.382$). The model meets the US Space Force's <5% TMD error guideline (e.g., Oliveira et al., 2021) and shows strong agreement with GRACE-FO ($RMSE = 0.067 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $R = 0.681$), confirming its accuracy across a solar cycle. The Eigen-Decomposition model performs well under quiet geomagnetic conditions, as validated by GRACE-FO data and statistical analysis, but its accuracy decreases during storm-time and solar maximum phases due to complex drivers. To improve robustness, ongoing efforts employ machine learning techniques to capture nonlinear variability beyond traditional methods. Although the ~133-day repeat cycle of Swarm-C limits temporal coverage, the 7-year data set provides valuable insights. Future enhancements will benefit from integrating multi-mission data (e.g., GRACE-FO, CHAMP) and data assimilation approaches.

Data Availability Statement

All TMD data and models used in this study are openly available. Satellite data from Swarm and GRACE-FO were obtained via the European Space Agency (ESA, 2025). Thermospheric model outputs were generated using JB2008 (Bowman et al., 2008; SpaceWx, 2025), NRLMSIS2.0 (CCMC, 2025; Emmert et al., 2020), and the CAJIN empirical model (Calabia & Jin, 2019). Ap index data were sourced from NASA's OMNIWeb (OMNIWeb, 2025), and solar proxy data, such as the Mg II core-to-wing index, were obtained from LASP (LASP, 2025). The Eigen-Decomposition analysis for dominant TMD modes was implemented using MATLAB code developed by the author (Owolabi, 2025), and is publicly available on Zenodo.

References

- Acciarini, G., Brown, E., Berger, T., Guhathakurta, M., Parr, J., Bridges, C., & Baydin, A. G. (2024). Improving thermospheric density predictions in low-Earth orbit with machine learning. *Space Weather*, 22(2), e2023SW003652. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023SW003652>
- Bandikova, T., McCullough, C., Gerhard, L. K., Save, H., & Christophe, B. (2019). GRACE accelerometer data transplant. *Advances in Space Research*, 64, 623644. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2019.05.02>
- Baruah, Y., Roy, S., Sinha, S., Palmerio, E., Pal, S., Oliveira, D. M., & Nandy, D. (2024). The loss of the Starlink satellites in February 2022: How moderate geomagnetic storms can adversely affect assets in low-earth orbit. *Space Weather*, 22(4), e2023SW003716. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023SW003716>
- Bowman, B. R., Tobiska, W. K., Marcos, F. A., Huang, C. Y., Lin, C. S., & Burke, W. J. (2008). A new empirical thermospheric density model JB2008 using new solar and geomagnetic indices. In *In proceedings of the AIAA/AAS astrodynamics specialist conference and exhibit* (pp. 18–21). <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2008-6438>
- Bowman, B. R., Tobiska, W. K., Marcos, F. A., & Valladares, C. (2007). The JB2006 empirical thermospheric density model. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 774–793. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2007.10.002>
- Bruinsma, S. (2015). The DTM-2013 thermosphere model. *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate*, 5, A1. <https://doi.org/10.1051/swsc/2017008>
- Bruinsma, S., Siemes, C., Emmert, J. T., & Mlynczak, M. G. (2023). Description and comparison of 21st century thermosphere data. *Advances in Space Research*, 72(12), 5476–5489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2022.09.038>
- Burns, A. G., Wang, W., & Qian, L. (2021). Neutral composition in the upper atmosphere. *Geophysical Monograph Series*, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119815631.ch6>

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- Calabia, A., & Jin, S. G. (2016). Thermospheric mass density variations during the March 2015 geomagnetic storm from GRACE accelerometers. In *Proceeding of progress in electromagnetics research symposium (PIERS2016)*, (Vol. 8–11 pp. 4976–4980). <https://doi.org/10.1109/PIERS.2016.7735812>
- Calabia, A., & Jin, S. G. (2016). New modes and mechanisms of thermospheric mass density variations from GRACE accelerometers. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *121*(11), 11191–11212. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JA022594>
- Calabia, A., & Jin, S. G. (2019). Solar cycle, seasonal, and asymmetric dependencies of thermospheric mass density disturbances due to magnetospheric forcing. *Annales Geophysicae*, *37*(5), 989–1003. <https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-37-989-2019>
- Calabia, A., Lu, G., & Bolaji, O. S. (2023). Editorial: Advances on upper-atmosphere characterization for geodetic space weather research and applications. *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, *10*, 1211582. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2023.1211582>
- Calabia, A., Tang, G., & Jin, S. G. (2020). Assessment of new thermospheric mass density model using NRLMSISE-00 model, GRACE, Swarm-C, and APOD observations. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, *199*, 105207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2020.105207>
- CCMC. (2025). NRLMSIS 2.0 atmospheric model: 18 June 2020 release (version: 2.0) [Software]. *Community Coordinated Modeling Center*. Retrieved from <https://map.nrl.navy.mil/map/pub/nrl/NRLMSIS/NRLMSIS2.0/>
- Ciraci, E., Velicogna, I., & Swenson, S. (2020). Continuity of the mass loss of the world's glaciers and ice caps from the GRACE and GRACE Follow-On missions. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *47*(9), e2019GL086926. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL086926>
- Elvidge, S., Godinez, H. C., & Angling, M. J. (2016). Improved forecasting of thermospheric densities using multi-model ensembles. *Geoscientific Model Development*, *9*(6), 2279–2292. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-2279-2016>
- Emmert, J. T., Drob, D. P., Picone, J. M., Siskind, D. E., Jones, M., Jr., Mlyneczek, M. G., et al. (2020). NRLMSIS 2.0: A whole-atmosphere empirical model of temperature and neutral species densities. *Earth and Space Science*, *7*(3), e2020EA001321. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001321>
- ESA. (2025). Swarm satellite mission data portal [Dataset]. *European Space Agency*. Retrieved from <https://swarm-diss.eo.esa.int>
- Fang, T.-W., Kubaryk, A., Goldstein, D., Li, Z., Fuller-Rowell, T., Millward, G., et al. (2022). Space weather environment during the SpaceX starlink satellite loss in February 2022. *Space Weather*, *20*(11), e2022SW003193. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022SW003193>
- Gondelach, D. J., & Linares, R. (2021). Real-time thermospheric density estimation via radar and GPS tracking data assimilation. *Space Weather*, *19*(4), e2020SW002620. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020SW002620>
- Guo, J., Wan, W., Forbes, J. M., Sutton, E., Nerem, R. S., & Bruinsma, S. (2008). Interannual and latitudinal variability of the thermosphere density annual harmonics. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *113*(A8), A08301. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008ja013056>
- He, J., Astafyeva, E., Yue, X., Pedatella, N. M., Lin, D., Fuller-Rowell, T. J., et al. (2023). Comparison of empirical and theoretical models of the thermospheric density enhancement during the 3–4 February 2022 geomagnetic storm. *Space Weather*, *21*(9), e2023SW003521. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023SW003521>
- Kodikara, T., Carter, B., & Zhang, K. (2018). The first comparison between Swarm-C accelerometer-derived thermospheric densities and physical and empirical model estimates. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *123*(6), 5068–5086. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017JA025118>
- Krauss, S., Temmer, M., Veronig, A., Baur, O., & Lammer, H. (2015). Thermosphere and geomagnetic response to interplanetary coronal mass ejections observed by ACE and GRACE: Statistical results. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *120*(10), 8848–8860. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021702>
- Landerer, F. W., Flechtner, F. M., Save, H., Webb, F. H., Bandikova, T., Bertiger, W. I., et al. (2020). Extending the global mass change data record: GRACE follow on instrument and science data performance. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *47*(12), e2020GL088306. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL088306>
- LASP. (2025). Mg II core-to-wing solar proxy data [Dataset]. *Laboratory for Atmospheric and Space Physics*. Retrieved from https://laspl.colorado.edu/lisird/data/sorce_mg_index
- Lei, J., Matsuo, T., Dou, X., Sutton, E., & Luan, X. (2012). Annual and semiannual variations of thermospheric density: EOF analysis of CHAMP and GRACE data. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *117*(A1), A01310. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JA017324>
- Lin, D., Wang, W., Garcia-Sage, K., Yue, J., Merkin, V., McInerney, J. M., et al. (2022). Thermospheric neutral density variation during the “SpaceX” storm: Implications from physics-based whole geospace modeling. *Space Weather*, *20*(12), e2022SW003254. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022SW003254>
- Liu, H., Hirano, T., & Watanabe, S. (2013). Empirical model of the thermospheric mass density based on CHAMP satellite observation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *118*(2), 843–848. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgra.50144>
- Liu, H., Lühr, H., Henize, V., & Köhler, W. (2005). Global distribution of the thermospheric total mass density derived from champ. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *110*(A4), A04301. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JA010741>
- Liu, H., Lühr, H., & Watanabe, S. (2007). Climatology of the equatorial thermospheric mass density anomaly. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *112*(A5), 305–311. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006ja012199>
- Liu, H., Yamamoto, M., & Lühr, H. (2009). Wave-4 pattern of the equatorial mass density anomaly: A thermospheric signature of tropical deep convection. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *36*(18), L18104. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009GL039865>
- Marcos, F. A. (1990). Accuracy of atmospheric drag models at low satellite altitudes. *Advances in Space Research*, *10*(3–4), 417–422. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1177\(90\)90381-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1177(90)90381-9)
- Matsuo, T., Fedrizzi, M., Fuller-Rowell, T. J., & Codrescu, M. V. (2012). Data assimilation of thermospheric mass density. *Space Weather*, *10*(5), S05002. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012SW000773>
- Matsuo, T., & Forbes, J. M. (2010). Principal modes of thermospheric density variability: Empirical orthogonal function analysis of CHAMP 2001–2008 data. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *115*(A7). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009ja015109>
- Mehta, P. M., Linares, R., & Sutton, E. K. (2018). A quasi-physical dynamic reduced order model for thermospheric mass density via Hermitian space-dynamic mode decomposition. *Space Weather*, *16*(5), 569–588. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018SW001840>
- Oliveira, D. M., & Zesta, E. (2019). Satellite orbital drag during magnetic storms. *Space Weather*, *17*(11), 1510–1533. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019SW002287>
- Oliveira, D. M., & Zesta, E. (2024). Inter-hemispheric energy input into the Ionosphere-thermosphere system: What we can and cannot learn from DMSP observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *129*(4), e2024JA032486. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JA032486>
- Oliveira, D. M., Zesta, E., Mehta, P. M., Licata, R. J., Pilinski, M. D., Kent Tobiska, W., & Hayakawa, H. (2021). The current state and future directions of modeling thermosphere density enhancements during extreme magnetic storms. *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Science*, *8*(764144). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2021.764144>
- Oliveira, D. M., Zesta, E., Schuck, P. W., & Sutton, E. K. (2017). Thermosphere global time response to geomagnetic storms caused by coronal mass ejections. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *122*(10), 10762–10782. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017ja024006>
- OMNIWeb. (2025). OMNI data for geomagnetic and solar activity indices [Dataset]. *NASA*. Retrieved from <https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/form/dx1.html>

- Owolabi, C. (2025). Empirical eigenmode extraction of thermospheric mass density: MATLAB implementation [Software]. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15627360>
- Owolabi, C., Ruan, H., Yamazaki, Y., Kaka, R. O., Akinola, O. O., & Yoshikawa, A. (2022). Ionospheric current variations by empirical orthogonal function analysis: Solar activity dependence and longitudinal differences. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, *127*(1), e2021JA029903. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JA029903>
- Owolabi, C., Ruan, H., Yamazaki, Y., Li, J., Zhong, J., Eyelade, A. V., et al. (2021). Empirical modeling of ionospheric current using empirical orthogonal function analysis and artificial neural network. *Space Weather*, *19*(11), e2021SW002831. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021SW002831>
- Picone, J. M., Hedin, A. E., Drob, D. P., & Aikin, A. C. (2002). NRLMSISE-00 empirical model of the atmosphere: Statistical comparisons and scientific issues. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *107*(A12), 1468. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JA009430>
- Ruan, H., Lei, J., Dou, X., Liu, S., & Aa, E. (2018). An exospheric temperature model based on CHAMP observations and TIEGCM simulations. *Space Weather*, *16*(2), 147–156. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017SW001759>
- Siemes, C., de Teixeira da Encarnação, J., Doornbos, E., van den IJssel, J., Kraus, J., Perešty, R., et al. (2016). Swarm accelerometer data processing from raw accelerations to thermospheric neutral densities. *Earth Planets and Space*, *68*(1), 92. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40623-016-0474-5>
- Solomon, S. C., Qian, L., Didkovsky, L. V., Viereck, R. A., & Woods, T. N. (2011). Causes of low thermospheric density during the 2007–2009 solar minimum. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *116*, A00H07. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JA016508>
- SpaceWx. (2025). JB2008 empirical thermospheric model [Software]. *Space*. Retrieved from <https://spacewx.com/jb2008/>
- Sutton, E. K., Cable, S. B., Lin, C. S., Qian, L., & Weimer, D. R. (2012). Thermospheric basis functions for improved dynamic calibration of semi-empirical models. *Space Weather*, *10*, S10001. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012SW000827>
- Sutton, E. K., Forbes, J. M., Nerem, R. S., & Woods, T. N. (2006). Neutral density response to the solar flares of October and November, 2003. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *33*(22). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006gl027737>
- Sutton, E. K., Nerem, R. S., & Forbes, J. M. (2007). Density and winds in the thermosphere deduced from accelerometer data. *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, *44*(6), 1210–1219. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.28641>
- Tobiska, W. K., Bouwer, D., & Bowman, B. R. (2008). The development of new solar indices for use in thermospheric density modeling. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, *70*(5), 803–819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2007.11.001>
- Tobiska, W. K., Bowman, B. R., Bouwer, D., Cruz, A., Wahl, K., Pilinski, M., et al. (2021). The SET HASDM density database. *Space Weather*, *19*(19), e2020SW002682. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020SW002682>
- Viereck, R., Puga, L., McMullin, D., Judge, D., Weber, M., & Tobiska, W. K. (2001). The Mg II index: A proxy for solar EUV. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *28*(7), 1343–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000GL012551>
- Vourlidas, A., & Bruinsma, S. (2018). EUV irradiance inputs to thermospheric density models: Open issues and path forward. *Space Weather*, *16*(1), 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017SW001725>
- Weimer, D. R. (2005). Improved ionospheric electrodynamic models and application to calculating joule heating rates. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *110*(A5), A05306. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004ja010884>
- Weng, L., Lei, J., Zhong, J., Dou, X., & Fang, H. (2020). A machine-learning approach to derive long-term trends of thermospheric density. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *47*(6), e2020GL087140. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020gl087140>
- Xiong, C., Lühr, H., Schmidt, M., Bloßfeld, M., & Rudenko, S. (2018). An empirical model of the thermospheric mass density derived from CHAMP satellite. *Annales Geophysicae*, *36*(4), 1141–1152. <https://doi.org/10.5194/angeo-36-1141-2018>
- Yang, X., Weng, L., Lei, J., Zhu, X., Ruan, H., Ren, D., et al. (2024). Evaluation of the exospheric temperature modeling from different empirical orthogonal functions. *Space Weather*, *22*(1), e2023SW003549. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023SW003549>
- Yang, X., Zhu, X. Q., Weng, L. B., & Yang, S. G. (2022). A new exospheric temperature model based on CHAMP and GRACE measurements. *Remote Sensing*, *14*(20), 5198. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14205198>
- Yu, T., Ren, Z., Yu, Y., & Wan, W. (2020). A new method for deriving the nightside thermospheric density based on guvi dayside limb observations. *Space Weather*, *18*(2), e2019SW002304. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019SW002304>
- Zhang, Y., Yu, J., Chen, J., & Sang, J. (2021). An empirical atmospheric density calibration model based on long short-term memory neural network. *Atmosphere*, *12*(7), 925. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12070925>